

Grain yield in various localities of Tanjong Karang (Malaysia) during season with and without brown planthopper (BPH) outbreaks. ^a

Locality	Grain yield (t/ha)							
	Crops without BPH infestation						Crops with BPH infestation	
	1974-75 MS	1975 OS	1975-76 MS	1976 OS	Av		1976-77 MS	1977 OS
				MS	OS			
Sawah Sempadan	3.09	2.87	2.91	3.08	3.00	2.97	3.56	3.24
Sg. Burong	3.08	4.15	3.73	3.58	3.40	3.87	2.54	1.80
Sekinchan	4.77	5.23	4.68	4.51	4.73	4.87	4.49	4.73
Sg. Leman	3.88	3.18	3.77	4.25	3.82	3.72	2.56	0.92
Sg. Pasir Panjang	3.40	3.05	3.04	4.17	3.22	3.61	2.83	1.38
Average	3.64	3.70	3.63	3.92	3.63	3.81	3.20	2.41

^a MS = main season, OS = off-season.

affected crops, on the average, yielded 53, 75, and 62% less than the uninfested crop (see table). In the 1976-77 main-season crops where infestation was less severe, yield reductions were 25.3, 33, and 12.0%, respectively. In Sekinchan, yield losses were only 3-5%, primarily because that area's paddy was heavily infested only at the late stage (near harvest). In Sungai Burong, Sungai Leman, and Sungai Pasir Panjang, the crops were affected about 1 to 1.5 months after transplanting.

The yield losses noted above, although a consequence of the BPH outbreak, were not only due to direct BPH damage. In some areas where insecticides were applied heavily, an upsurge of stem borers (mostly *Chilo polychrysus*) severely damaged crops.

The overall losses to the BPH outbreak were substantial. As much as 25% of the yield (or 870 kg/ha) was lost in 1977, but only about 1%, or 34 kg/ha was lost in the 1976-77 main season. The losses amounted to about \$4.16 million and

\$0.17 million (at the minimum guaranteed price of \$14.29/60.48 kg of paddy) for the 1977 off-season and 1976-77 main-season crops. Clearly, efforts to prevent epidemic outbreaks of BPH should be the core strategy in BPH management. It is more important to identify the root of the problems and to seek sound solutions than to repetitiously attempt to treat the symptoms, as is often done during BPH outbreaks. ■

Sheath rot outbreak in the Punjab

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Sheath rot of rice caused by *Acrocyndrium oryzae* (Sawada) was first reported in India from Hyderabad, A.P., in 1974. In the 1978-79 kharif severe infection on semidwarf rice varieties at the PAU Research Farm, Kapurthala, was observed. The disease was also widespread at moderate to severe intensities in farmers' fields. Sheath rot was observed on improved varieties planted in the Punjab — IR8, Jaya, PR106, and PR103. The most susceptible was PR106 (see photo). Disease incidence and severity averaged 30% and 70% throughout the Punjab. Grain chaffiness was 15 to 35%. In severe cases, 100% seed sterility and no panicle emergence were observed.

Diseased portions of the flag leaf sheaths were used in pathogenicity tests.

Cultures of *A. oryzae* were grown on five substrates: pearl millet grains, paddy grains, paddy straw bits, paddy husk, and

Sheath rot damage on PR106.

PDA. The cultures on the first 4 substrates were incubated for 15 days; the PDA culture was incubated for 8 days. PR106 plants were inoculated at the booting stage. Single grains, bits, or husks with the culture were inserted inside the flag leaf sheath just above the floret. For PDA culture, ½ ml of spore suspension was injected into each flag leaf sheath. Disease was recorded 20 days after inoculation.

Inoculation by inserting paddy and pearl millet grain culture produced typical disease symptoms, and infected 75% and 70% of the inoculated tillers, respectively. Other methods were less effective. Spore injection produced atypical symptoms. Carbendazim was effective (see table) against the disease. ■

Effect of fungicidal sprays on sheath rot. Punjab Agricultural University, India.

Treatment	Disease intensity (av for 100 plants)
Carbendazim @ 0.1%	3.3
Captafol @ 0.15%	4.0
Mancozeb @ 0.3%	4.8
Hinosan @ 0.1%	4.0
Control - water spray	6.5